

Teaching for Tomorrow: A Hands-On Teaching Concept on Integrating AI and Future Skills in a Master's Curriculum

Roederer Julia*¹, Eilers, Karen²

February 2026

¹ Offenburg University, Offenburg, Germany

² Business & Law School, Hamburg, Germany

Abstract

Universities are increasingly acknowledging the need to equip students with the skills necessary to work critically, responsibly, and confidently with digital technologies. Although many frameworks describe these skills, translating them into concrete teaching and learning practices in higher education remains challenging. By presenting a comprehensive overview of fundamental design principles and contextual factors, this paper provides a foundation of knowledge that can be applied to a variety of settings. Furthermore, it offers insights that can assist educators in the integration of technology-related future skills into digitally enriched higher education curricula. This paper presents a hands-on teaching concept that demonstrates how technology-related future skills can be developed in a Master's program in Business Psychology. Rather than emphasizing technical mastery, this approach encourages critical engagement with technologies, reflective experimentation, and the development of a digital agency.

Keywords: Future Skills; AI adoption; Curriculum Design; Hands-on Learning; Business Psychology; Digital Competence

Introduction

In recent years, universities have increasingly recognized the urgent need to equip students with future skills, especially digital and artificial intelligence competencies, that go beyond traditional disciplinary knowledge (Mejía-Manzano et al. 2024). Various frameworks offer plans to develop curricula for these skills. However, universities continue to face challenges implementing these models into university curricula (Ng et al. 2023; Maznev et al. 2024). Furthermore, empirical evidence indicates that collaborative, experiential learning environments are essential for successfully fostering these competencies (Benvenuti et al. 2023; Gupta & Jaiswal 2024). However, detailed, real-world examples of curriculum design and instructional approaches are scarce. This paper aims to address this gap by presenting a case description of a “Future Skills” module within a Master’s program in Business Psychology. We contribute to the growing conversation about how universities can transition from abstract future skills models to meaningful curricular transformations that prepare students for the challenges of a digital transformative environment. It is exemplified how future skills development can be embedded in authentic, practice-oriented university curricula. Furthermore, it is demonstrated how teaching and assessment methods can be aligned with evidence-based principles, such as collaborative learning, situated cognition, and personalized learning paths (Modran et al. 2024; Toohey et al. 2025; Wang 2026).

Theoretical Background

Structured frameworks are key to developing future skills in higher education (Cosgrove & Cachia 2025; Ehlers 2024). These frameworks work best with practical, learner-centered teaching methods. Active learning, project-based learning, and industry collaboration get students to use digital tools and AI technologies. This hands-on approach lets students evaluate and apply these resources in different situations, fostering adaptability and a deeper understanding (Naaser et al. 2025). This section will explore these frameworks and teaching methods and evaluate their effectiveness in enhancing learning success.

Future Skills Frameworks and Models

Several frameworks have been developed to define “future skills.” The contents are difficult to define because we are trying to integrate relevant competencies that will be necessary in a future reality that does not yet exist. However, existing conceptual work provides good guidelines for focusing on the relevant skills that will enable current students to succeed in their future careers (Rampelt et al. 2025).

Developed by the European Commission, the **DigComp framework** defines digital competence in five areas: information literacy, communication, content creation, safety,

and problem solving (Cosgrove & Cachia 2025). It provides comprehensive guidelines for incorporating digital skills into curricula, ensuring that students are prepared for the digital world.

Building upon digital competencies, **AI competence models** emphasize AI literacy and skills such as critical thinking, ethical understanding, and effectively interacting with AI systems (Haase 2024; Tenberga & Daniela 2024). These models can specifically guide universities in incorporating AI-related content into courses (Tondeur et al. 2023).

The future skills triple helix-model model highlights the interconnectedness of subject-specific skills, task-related competencies, and the social environment. It emphasizes the importance of aligning educational goals with real-world demands and serves as a guiding framework for universities adopting holistic approaches to skill development (Kleimola & Leppisaari 2022).

In sum, these frameworks are helpful to define a focus for developing relevant future skills in higher education. In the face of various frameworks and contexts, universities are increasingly designing their own models to develop future skills (Mejía-Manzano et al. 2024). Examples of such initiatives include the Philipps-Universität Marburg (Marskills) and ETH Zurich. Explicit models for future skills are characterized by the incorporation of generic competencies into their respective curricula (Jääskelä et al. 2018). These competencies are intended to be developed through active, partnership-rich designs supported by digital tools and aligned with international frameworks (e.g., Naseer et al. 2025). However, robust, long-term evidence and comprehensive coverage of all future skill domains are still emerging.

Pedagogical Approaches

Being clear about the relevant future skills that should be developed is the one thing. The other thing is how to help students actually develop these skills. To translate future skills into practice, various pedagogical approaches can be applied. In the following section, we outline three approaches that are proven to be empirically successful and are embedded into a curriculum module described in this paper.

Active and Project-Based Learning: These strategies promote student engagement by involving them in hands-on projects that simulate real-world challenges (Naaser et al. 2025). Students apply theories to practice, thereby enhancing their critical thinking, problem-solving, and adaptability skills (Alt et al. 2023). Universities encourage a deeper understanding of AI technologies by allowing students to explore and evaluate multiple tools.

Collaborative and Industry-Integrated Learning: Through collaboration with industry partners, universities provide authentic learning experiences that improve employability and practical preparedness. These experiences help students position themselves within

professional contexts and develop relevant skills (Naaser et al. 2025; Ornellas et al. 2019).

Integration of AI and Learning Analytics: AI tools and learning analytics provide personalized learning experiences and facilitate adaptive feedback and self-regulated learning (Wang 2026). These tools help students develop digital agency and understand the practical applications and limitations of AI (Çelik et al. 2024; Kleimola & Leppisaari 2022).

Empirical Evidence

Empirical studies have consistently demonstrated that integrating structured frameworks and learner-centered pedagogical approaches enhances higher education outcomes. These methodologies have been successful in three key areas:

1. Skill Acquisition: Integrating AI and digital competence models improves technical and soft skills. For example, project-based and industry-enriched curricula have notably increased critical thinking, communication, and digital literacy skills (Karunaratne & Calma 2023; Podlaski et al. 2025).

2. Practical Application: Students who actively engage with AI tools report improved abilities to assess and apply these technologies across various use cases (Cabero-Almenara et al. 2021). This experiential learning approach helps students develop a personal stance on AI and fosters an informed, critical understanding of its capabilities and ethical implications (Benvenuti et al. 2023; Gupta & Jaiswal 2024).

3. Feedback and Adaptability: AI-enhanced learning environments provide real-time feedback, promoting adaptability and self-directed learning. This approach supports the development of skills that align with personal learning goals and industry standards (Çelik et al. 2024; Daniel, Msambwa, & Wen 2025).

Despite positive outcomes, challenges remain, particularly regarding standardized assessments and integrating emotional skills into curricula. Continuous adjustments and research are necessary to address these issues and optimize learning environments (Deroncele-Acosta et al. 2025; González-Salamanca et al. 2020). In conclusion, integrating frameworks such as DigComp and AI competence models with active learning methodologies facilitates the systematic development of future skills in university settings. Fostering student engagement through practical exploration and self-assessment cultivates an understanding of AI in academia real-world applications, as evidenced by research in the field (Cabero-Almenara et al. 2021).

Case Description

The competency model of the Master in Business Psychology. A competency model was developed for the recently established "Master in Business Psychology" (MBP), drawing from the theoretical background. This model conceptualizes the future skills and competencies of business psychologists in the context of prototypical future working contexts. The MBP Competency Model, illustrated in Figure 1, is a multidimensional framework designed to elucidate the functional relationships between specific core competencies and personal development. Rather than serving as a direct intervention, the model offers a theoretical framework for understanding how diverse psychological and behavioral domains interact to promote professional growth.

Figure 1: Key Competencies "Master Business Psychology"

The MBP Competency Model is structurally aligned with the BESSI domains (Soto et al. 2022), which categorize socio-emotional skills into functional areas. Specifically, the model incorporates "Social Engagement Skills" (capacities to actively engage with others), "Innovation Skills" (the ability to engage with novel ideas), and "Self-Management Skills" (capacities used to effectively pursue goals and complete tasks). These domains ensure that the model covers both interpersonal effectiveness and individual productivity.

Furthermore, the MBP Competency Model incorporates the "Framework model for positive self-management" (Braun & Ziemke 2017). This model serves as an explanatory link, illustrating how the application of positive psychological techniques and self-management competencies (such as agility or time management) leads to increased mental strength. According to this model, mental strength—comprising factors like resilience, optimism, and self-efficacy—functions as a mediator that ultimately results in long-term positive outcomes such as higher job satisfaction and reduced stress levels (Braun & Ziemke 2017). The MBP Competency Model acknowledges the strengths of character and well-being, which are defined by Peterson and Seligman (2004) as wisdom, courage, and humanity. These virtues serve as the ethical and personal foundation for the model's technical and methodological skills, including "Analytical-Methodological Strengths" and "Resource Orientation."

The model's theoretical framework is supported by empirical evidence. Research has demonstrated that the cultivation of socio-emotional resources and positive psychological states not only enhances individual productivity but also substantially predicts higher life satisfaction through improved resilience and coping mechanisms (Cohn et al. 2009; Soto et al. 2022).

In this paper, we will select several competency areas of the MBP Competency Model and demonstrate the implementation of this model in the systematic development of these competencies within two modules of the Master Business Psychology curriculum. The primary focus of this study is on the cultivation of "innovation" and "self-management" competencies, which are exhibited through three modules. A detailed description and guideline are provided to encourage the adoption and/or modification of the approach according to specific needs and goals of higher education.

The MBP integrates three specific "Future Skills" modules: 1) New Technologies in Practice, which is focused in our paper as a case, 2) Organizing a Learning Expedition, and 3) Conduct the Learning Expedition (see also "Integration of the Module in Curriculum"). Those three modules align education with the evolving demands of the workforce. They bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application, empowering students to critically engage with AI technologies. These modules emphasize experiential learning. Students are encouraged to actively test, evaluate, and develop their personal perspectives on AI tools. This hands-on method ensures that students understand AI technologies and form informed opinions about their use and impact.

While the modules cover a range of competencies, including creativity and innovation, they primarily focus on enabling students to effectively and knowledgeably engage with AI technologies. By fostering critical and evaluative thinking, the modules prepare students to navigate and contribute to the future workforce, where AI plays a central role. Through this approach, students learn to assess the ethical implications and practical applications of AI tools, thereby enhancing their adaptability and problem-solving abilities in professional settings.

Description of Module "New Technologies in Practice"

In this paper we want to focus on providing hands-on guidance on the conduction of a two-day block seminar entitled "New Technologies in Practice" which was implemented in the Master's programme in Business Psychology with 15 students. The seminar addressed the growing relevance of AI for professional practice in business psychology work contexts, with a particular emphasis on applied understanding, critical reflection, and responsible use of digital technologies in recruiting and people development.

The module was delivered in a block format consisting of one and a half intensive seminar days followed by a half-day dedicated to student project presentations. Learning activities combined short theoretical inputs with collaborative tasks, guided reflection, and hands-on experimentation with AI tools. An overview regarding the learning goals, methods used, format and assessment can be seen in Table 1. The assessment was designed as a practice-oriented group project. Student teams explored concrete AI application scenarios in the field of human resources, experimented with relevant tools, evaluated benefits and limitations, and presented their insights in a final pitch. Assessment criteria were co-developed with the students to strengthen transparency,

ownership, and evaluation competence. In the following sections, we describe the learning content and activities. The whole instructional guide can be found in Appendix A.

Table 1: Overview of Module “New Technologies in Practice”

Learning Goals	<p>After completion of the module, students are able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● critically evaluate innovative technologies (AI-based) ● analyze their potential applications and ● situate them within the context of business psychology
Used Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Groupwork ● Self-reflection ● Peer Interviews ● Presentation ● Discussion ● Experimentation ● AI Demo Interviews
Format	<p>Blockseminar splitted in two blocks: 1,5 days: Learning about new technologies 0,5 days: Presentations of the students</p>
Assessment	<p>Pitch presentation (20 min per group) and discussion (10 min per group)</p>

Step 1: Opening

The seminar followed an experiential and participatory learning design. We started with an opening: After a short introduction of the lecturer, the learning goals we want to achieve in this module got explained. At the outset, the lecturer introduced a draft for a shared “modus operandi” emphasizing mutual responsibility, active participation, experimentation, and psychological safety. Using the “1-2-4-All” method of the liberating structures (n.d.), students adapted these principles to their own needs, for example by defining norms for collaboration, autonomy in group work, and break structures. Based on these, the students commit themselves to their way of working and assume the role of co-constructors of knowledge, as opposed to merely passive recipients of instruction.

Step 2: Reflecting on Future Skills

After this opening, the students started in the “Reflecting on Future Skills” part of the workshop: Students reflected on the question: “*What skills, beyond disciplinary knowledge, do you want to take with you from your studies?*” They start with an individual reflection. After that they interviewed each other in pairs, and share their results in the plenum. 17 skill aspects were identified, including self-efficacy, self-

awareness, confidence, networking, flexibility, and openness. These insights were later revisited to align seminar content with students' expectations and perceived relevance.

Following an introduction to the MBP competency model (see Figure 1) that serves as the foundation for the master's program, students completed a self-assessment survey that served to evaluate their current level of future skills. Based on this reflection, learners defined individual development goals for the semester and selected three future skills they intended to focus on. This step served to anchor subsequent learning activities in personal relevance and self-regulated learning processes, which are considered key enablers of sustainable competence development in digital learning environments.

Step 3: Foundations of AI

To support the development of technological-based future skills (e. g. Openness to technology, working in a team with people and technology, using analysis tools, critical thinking, technological literacy, recognizing and utilizing the strength of new technologies) the next step of the workshop focuses on providing foundations of AI. To gauge students' baseline understanding, they worked in small groups to collect terms they associated with AI. This activity provided valuable insight into their existing mental models. We observed that students were familiar with several key notions, such as prompting, bias, neural networks, and algorithms, yet their understanding of these terms was often superficial. In addition, concepts not directly related to AI (e.g., blockchain) were mentioned, indicating blurred conceptual boundaries.

The majority of students had minimal prior experience with AI, having utilized only a single AI tool prior to the seminar. To establish a shared foundation, the initial content block introduced core AI concepts alongside a brief historical overview. Students quickly recognized that definitions of "artificial intelligence" are not fixed but evolve over time. After the presentation they discussed their terms they summarized before and explained how they really belong to AI and deleted terms, which has nothing to do with AI.

After the lunch break, we deepened the conceptual input. We explained the relationships between AI, machine learning, deep learning, and generative AI. To facilitate comprehension of language model functionality, probabilistic text generation was illustrated using the German fairy tale Rumpelstilzchen. Building on optimization approaches such as fine-tuning and reinforcement learning, students discussed how these methods shape outputs. For example, how results follow probabilistic language distributions, are influenced by dialogic context, and are often optimized for positive human evaluation, without necessarily being correct or true.

To conclude this unit, students watched the video "*Gen-KI Basics*" by Prof. Dr. Chris Biemann and discussed open questions, new insights, and identified risks. Finally, they transferred the topic to both academic and professional contexts: in groups, they explored where AI is already used in practice and, in a second step, collaboratively

compiled an online table of AI tools they currently use AI in their studies, including perceived benefits and risks. This sequence enabled students without a technical background to develop a functional understanding of how contemporary AI systems operate. Overall, the conceptual grounding aimed to empower learners to critically assess AI outputs and limitations rather than treating AI as a “black box.”

Step 4: Prompting and technology-enhanced experimentation

A central element of the seminar was the hands-on exploration of generative AI systems. Students worked with different AI tools and language models and engaged in structured prompting exercises, including role-based prompts, contextualization, prompt chaining, and variations in tone and output format. By systematically comparing outputs across prompts and tools, learners developed an applied understanding of how human input shapes AI-generated results.

This experimentation phase supported the development of digital agency, problem-solving skills, and reflective technology use. Students were encouraged to document situations in which AI performed effectively, where limitations became apparent, and which assumptions underpinned their interactions with the systems. Playful and creative tasks—such as generating images of highly unusual chairs—helped students realize the importance of precise qualifier terms in prompting, while also illustrating the inherent variability of generative outputs, as identical results are rarely produced.

Additional challenging exercises, such as attempting to generate images of people in unconventional positions without visual errors using different AI tools, or solving *Gandalf's Password* (Lakera n.d.), further deepened students' understanding of how generative AI systems operate. These activities made core principles of probabilistic generation, constraint handling, and model limitations tangible, while maintaining a high level of engagement and motivation among learners.

Step 5: Ethical, societal, and regulatory perspectives

As a warm-up for this section, students were presented with three AI-generated personal profiles created using *They See Your Photos* (n.d.), a tool that infers characteristics such as emotions, income range, clothing style, or political affiliation from a single image. Although all three images depicted the same lecturer, the resulting profiles differed substantially (see figure 2). This discrepancy served as a starting point for discussion and prompted students to reflect on how such divergent interpretations emerge from visually similar inputs.

Figure 2: The same person, but AI shows very different characteristics based on three pictures. What can we learn?” (Based on Diercks 2026)

The discussion highlighted that AI-generated outputs do not represent objective truths about individuals but are probabilistic inferences based on patterns learned from training

data. Students recognized that concepts such as personality traits or political attitudes have no intrinsic meaning for AI systems; instead, they are modeled as statistical associations. At the same time, the exercise revealed that AI systems can reproduce and scale existing societal biases by mirroring common human assumptions based on visual cues. Consequently, AI outputs may appear plausible while remaining factually incorrect (Diercks 2026).

Building on these insights and their prior practical experiences, students critically examined ethical and societal challenges associated with AI use. Working in small groups, they analyzed selected problem areas of generative AI, including bias, explainability, power asymmetries, AI as critical infrastructure, diffusion of responsibility, and transparency. These themes were derived from a discussion paper by the German National Academy of Sciences Leopoldina (Simon et al. 2024). Group results were visualized and discussed in plenary sessions, fostering dialogical learning, perspective-taking, and collective sense-making. A key takeaway became particularly clear: everyone who uses AI bears responsibility for its outcomes and implications. After a brief synthesis of today's take-aways, the first seminar day concluded.

On the second seminar day, following an energizing opening activity and a recap of key insights, the EU AI Act was introduced as a regulatory framework for trustworthy AI. Learners applied the regulation to a concrete use case involving the implementation of an AI-based employee monitoring system for engagement and performance. Working collaboratively in groups, they examined the EU AI Act to identify relevant obligations for both providers and users of such systems. This case-based approach enabled students to connect abstract legal principles with real-world decision-making contexts. Overall, the activity aimed to strengthen regulatory literacy and ethical judgment in digitally mediated professional environments.

Step 6: Deep dive into AI in Recruiting

In this step, the focus shifted to a typical future work context for students of business psychology: recruiting. The session began with an open discussion prompted by the following scenario: *"You apply for a job and receive an invitation to a short interview conducted by an AI avatar"*. Most students expressed skepticism toward this situation. Common concerns included a perceived lack of appreciation by the organization (e.g., "they do not take the time to get to know me personally"), a feeling of limited influence over the interview process and outcome, and the absence of opportunities to gain meaningful information about the organization.

Following this initial discussion, students deepened their understanding through a structured input phase. They learned that AI is already being used across all stages of the personnel selection process and explored the most frequently cited organizational motivations for adopting AI in recruiting, such as increased efficiency, improved candidate quality, and enhanced fairness and objectivity (e.g., Black & van Esch 2020; Gonzalez et al. 2022). In addition, key challenges associated with AI implementation

were introduced and critically discussed. These included the technology dilemma (e.g., heterogeneous IT systems or insufficient data quality), the process dilemma (the need to analyze and redesign processes while addressing ethical and legal issues), the acceptance dilemma (HR professionals must adopt AI systems and applicants must accept their use), and the knowledge dilemma (limited understanding of AI functionality, application, and contextual implications).

Two concrete AI avatar applications were examined in more detail: Vera (Rottwilm 2018; Ullah & Witt 2018) and Tengai (Tengai 2023; 2026). Using Tengai, students experienced a simulated job interview with an AI avatar themselves. Subsequently, they discussed their experiences in pairs, reflecting on the questions: How did the interview feel from the applicant's perspective? How user-friendly was the interaction? What types of questions did the avatar ask? And on a scale from 1 to 10, how accurately did they believe the AI captured their personality and competencies?

Afterwards, students adopted the perspective of HR professionals and collaboratively discussed how HR professionals should respond to these developments. Suggested actions included being and staying curious and develop AI-related competencies, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration within the organization, increasing transparency through explainable AI practices (e.g., clarifying when AI is used, when humans make decisions, and how responsibilities are distributed), developing or supporting ethical AI guidelines, and actively sharing AI-related knowledge within the organization.

Step 7: Practice-oriented transfer and assessment

During an initial brainstorming session, students developed a wide range of potential challenges, in a business psychologist working life, such as structuring complex thoughts with the support of AI, organizing daily work routines more efficiently, accelerating the creation of business reports, or designing learning materials for trainees in an effective way. Working in small groups of two to three students, each team selected two challenges to pursue independently until the second block seminar (day three). The course assessment was designed as a practice-oriented group project. Student teams work on their own selected and concrete AI application scenarios in the field of human resources, experimented with relevant tools, evaluated their usefulness and limitations, and conducted interviews with practitioners to integrate external perspectives. The results will be presented and discussed in a final session. The explicit goal was to address a real-world challenge as comprehensively as possible using AI, to test different solution strategies, and to critically evaluate their outcomes.

After summarizing their key takeaways of the last two days, the first block seminar ends.

Between the two block sessions, students were offered one to two coaching appointments with the lecturer. These sessions provided opportunities for exchange and support, particularly in relation to complex challenges, ethical considerations, and legal questions. The university granted access to a variety of AI models and tools (some of

them designed to limit data usage by providers) including, for example, NotebookLM, OpenAI models, and Gemini.

In the second block seminar, students presented their assessment results in the form of a pitch presentation. The assessment criteria were co-developed with the students to foster transparency, ownership, and evaluative competence. The lecturer initially presented her proposed criteria for discussion and invited students to reflect on the question: "*What would you consider excellent performance in these pitches?*" The additional criteria collected via email were subsequently integrated into the final assessment framework.

The pitches were evaluated not only by the lecturer but also by peers. The deviations between peer assessments and the lecturer's evaluations were minimal, with a maximum difference of 0.3 grade points, indicating a high level of alignment between both assessment approaches. Final grades, including anonymized peer feedback and individualized qualitative feedback from the lecturer on how the pitches could be further developed for organizational contexts, were shared with the student groups.

This assessment format explicitly targeted future skills such as collaboration, critical evaluation of technology, communication skills, and the ability to transfer academic learning into professional practice. Overall, the block seminar demonstrates how technology-enhanced, interactive learning designs can support future skills development in higher education. By combining conceptual input, hands-on experimentation, reflective dialogue, and ethical and regulatory framing, the course created a learning environment in which students developed both practical competence and critical awareness in dealing with emerging digital technologies. The described approach is transferable to other higher education contexts, particularly in programs aiming to prepare learners for complex, technology-rich, and ethically sensitive professional environments.

Module Integration into the Curriculum

The previously described "New Technologies in Practice" module is interwoven with two other modules in the curriculum of the MBP that focus on future skills: Learning Expedition I and II.

Learning Expedition I: The module "Learning Expedition I" runs concurrently with "New Technologies in Practice" in the same semester. While the former provides theoretical underpinnings and an introduction to digital competencies, Learning Expedition I allows students to apply and expand these skills in real-world contexts.

In the course entitled "Learning Expedition I," students concentrate on establishing both individual and collective objectives and formulating a genuine, non-virtual international learning expedition to investigate innovation in practice. The objective of this initiative is to facilitate the collaborative design of a learning expedition that will enable participants to introduce themselves to a novel technology that is currently unfamiliar to them but

which they consider to be important for their future professional careers. The objective of this module is to facilitate a comprehensive exploration of the selected technology, with the ultimate goal of developing a well-informed perspective on it. The course places significant emphasis on organizational and budget planning, the selection of destinations with a forward-thinking approach, and the preparation for an actual expedition in the subsequent semester.

Students are encouraged to apply what they learned in the "New Technologies in Practice" seminar to the real-life settings explored in "Learning Expedition I." The objective of this initiative is to integrate digital competencies into the practical design of their learning expedition.

Learning Expedition II: The course "Learning Expedition II" is in the next semester. In it, students work together to plan their learning expedition, building on "Learning Expedition I" and the insights from the "New Technologies in Practice" seminar. This module focuses on conducting and managing the expedition, documenting and evaluating learning experiences and leadership and change management. Students document and evaluate their expedition outcomes and reflect on their learnings. This includes insights into digital transformation, leadership challenges and change management, explored through direct engagement with various international professionals.

Overall Integration and Outcomes: By interlinking these modules, the curriculum fosters key skills such as self-directed learning, the capacity to innovate, ethical reasoning, and global digital literacy. This initiative is designed to equip students with the skills necessary to critically evaluate and responsibly implement new technologies in a variety of settings. The modules facilitate a smooth transition from theoretical concepts to practical applications, thereby reinforcing the curriculum's experiential learning component. This prepares students for dynamic professional environments that demand technological proficiency and ethical sensitivity. The incorporation of block seminars and subsequent expeditions has been demonstrated to foster collaboration, team-based reflection, and peer-to-peer learning. This comprehensive approach is designed to equip students with the essential skills and knowledge necessary to excel in the field of business psychology.

Discussion

The "New Technologies in Practice" module yielded several key insights, emphasizing the contextual factors crucial for its success. The following three insights form the foundation of our discussion: 1) positive experiences with active experimenting getting a meta-perspective on AI and its impact, 2) the new role of the lecturer, and finally 3) the tension between experimentation and assessment.

Key Learnings and Educational Implications

Both qualitative observations and student feedback suggest that the experiential and participatory learning design supported deep engagement with AI technologies and their societal implications. Overall, the findings indicate that the described didactic sequence was effective in fostering future skills development. Student responses were positive, which was also reflected in the teaching evaluation. Learners particularly valued the opportunity to actively experiment with AI tools, discuss uncertainties openly, and critically reflect on limitations and risks rather than focusing on tool mastery alone.

A central learning outcome was the development of a *meta-perspective on AI*. By working with multiple tools and models, students gained an overview of different AI systems and developed an understanding of which tools are suitable for which purposes. This comparative exposure reduced initial hesitation and fostered confidence to experiment independently. Importantly, students reported that the seminar created a “safe space” for trial and error, which encouraged exploratory learning and reduced fear of making mistakes—an essential prerequisite for developing adaptive and innovative competencies.

The case also highlights a shift in the *role of the lecturer*. Rather than acting as an expert who fully controls content and tools, the lecturer assumed the role of a facilitator and co-learner. This approach required openness to experimentation and a willingness to engage with unfamiliar tools alongside students. Over time, this led to a dynamic learning environment in which students contributed their own discoveries, tools, and insights, thereby enriching the collective learning process. Such a model aligns with emerging understandings of teaching in rapidly evolving digital contexts, where continuous professional learning becomes a shared responsibility between educators and learners (Kong & Yang 2024; Wang et al. 2026).

One of the most critical challenges identified in this case concerns *assessment*. While future skills development benefits from open-ended exploration, experimentation, and reflection, higher education contexts still require summative evaluation and grading. The pitch-based assessment format addressed this tension by emphasizing synthesis, relevance, and communicative clarity. Students were challenged to present their insights concisely to a hypothetical management board, a perspective that many initially perceived as unfamiliar and demanding. Co-developing assessment criteria with students proved to be a productive strategy, fostering transparency, ownership, and shared understanding of quality. The high alignment between peer and lecturer assessments suggests that students developed evaluative competence and a realistic sense of performance standards. Nevertheless, the format also revealed limitations: the time constraint and performative nature of pitches may disadvantage students who require more space for nuanced reflection. As a result, a complementary reflection paper could be a valuable addition in future iterations, allowing students to elaborate on their

reasoning processes and reducing the weight placed solely on presentation performance.

Contextual Conditions and Transferability

The effectiveness of the described approach is closely linked to specific contextual conditions. In this section we want to shed light especially into three: 1) IT Infrastructure, 2) competencies and attitudes of the educators, and finally 3) the student prerequisites.

First, institutional *IT infrastructure* played a crucial role. Providing access to multiple AI tools and language models, including options with stricter data protection, enabled meaningful comparison, experimentation, and critical evaluation. Without such access, opportunities for developing a meta-perspective on AI would be significantly constrained.

Second, the approach presupposes certain *competencies and attitudes on the part of educators*. Facilitating exploratory AI learning requires tolerance for uncertainty, willingness to experiment publicly, and the ability to frame not knowing as a productive learning condition. This represents a departure from traditional teaching roles and highlights the importance of professional development for lecturers in future skills-oriented education.

Third, *student prerequisites* must be considered. The learning design assumes a degree of self-regulation, responsibility, and initiative, including the ability to independently explore tools and reflect on their use. While many students embraced this responsibility, such expectations may pose challenges in contexts where learners are accustomed to highly structured, pre-packaged learning formats. Providing explicit scaffolding for self-directed learning and gradually increasing autonomy may therefore be essential for broader transferability.

Conclusion

This paper introduces an innovative teaching concept that incorporates future skills, such as AI and digital competencies, into a Master's program in Business Psychology. The "New Technologies in Practice" module demonstrates how a practical, student-centered approach can bridge the gap between theoretical frameworks and real-world applications. By combining experiential learning with critical reflection on ethical and societal issues, students are empowered with digital agency and become deeply engaged.

Implementing this approach highlights the evolving role of educators as facilitators in exploratory learning environments and underscores the need for supportive institutional infrastructure and flexibility to experiment. Aligning student and peer assessments emphasizes the importance of co-developing evaluative criteria.

The module's success demonstrates its potential for adoption in various higher education settings where developing future skills is essential. As institutions adapt to digital transformations, this practice-oriented framework can serve as a model for cultivating the competencies necessary to excel in complex, technology-rich environments. Educators are encouraged to adopt these principles in their curricula to better prepare students for the dynamic challenges of the future workforce. The findings highlight the need for professional development programs that emphasize interpersonal skill development for teachers operating in AI-mediated learning environments.

Data Accessibility

No datasets, code, or structured materials were deposited in a public repository for this study. The manuscript is based on conceptual development and case-based descriptions, and it does not generate openly shareable data. Accordingly, no public data access link or DOI is provided.

Competing Interests

The authors have no competing interests to declare.

Ethics Approval

Ethics Approval was not required.

References

- Alt, D., Naamati-Schneider, L., & Weishut, D. J. N. (2023). Competency-based learning and formative assessment feedback as precursors of college students' soft skills acquisition. *Studies in Higher Education, 48*(12), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2023.2217203>
- Benvenuti, M., Cangelosi, A., Weinberger, A., Mazzoni, E., Benassi, M., Barbaresi, M., & Orsoni, M. (2023). Artificial intelligence and human behavioral development: A perspective on new skills and competences acquisition for the educational context. *Computers in Human Behavior, 148*(148), 107903. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2023.107903>
- Black, J. S., & van Esch, P. (2020). AI-enabled recruiting: What is it and how should a manager use it? *Business Horizons, 63*(2), 215–226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2019.12.001>
- Braun, O. L., & Ziemke, S. (2019). Theorie und Training mit Positiver Psychologie. In O. L. Braun (Ed.), *Selbstmanagement und Mentale Stärke im Arbeitsleben: Training und Evaluation* (pp. 1–20). https://doi.org/10.1007/9783662579091_1
- Cabero-Almenara, J., Guillén-Gámez, F. D., Ruiz-Palmero, J., & Palacios-Rodríguez, A. (2021). Digital competence of higher education professor according to DigCompEdu. Statistical research methods with ANOVA between fields of knowledge in different age ranges. *Education and Information Technologies, 26*(4), 4691–4708. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639021104765>
- Celik, I., Gedrimiene, E., Siklander, S., & Muukkonen, H. (2022). The affordances of artificial intelligence-based tools for supporting 21st-century skills: A systematic review of empirical research in higher education. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology, 40*(3). <https://doi.org/10.14742/ajet.9069>
- Cohn, M. A., Fredrickson, B. L., Brown, S. L., Mikels, J. A., & Conway, A. M. (2009). Happiness unpacked: Positive emotions increase life satisfaction by building resilience. *Emotion, 9*(3), 361–368. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0015952>
- Cosgrove, J., & Cachia, R. (2025). *DigComp 3.0: The European Digital Competence Framework* (5th ed.). Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/0001149>
- Daniel, K., Msambwa, M., M., & Wen, Z. (2025). Can Generative AI Revolutionise Academic Skills Development in Higher Education? A Systematic Literature Review. *European Journal of Education, 60*(1). <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejed.70036>

Deroncele-Acosta, A., Sayán-Rivera, R. M. E., Mendoza-López, A. D., & Norabuena-Figueroa, E. D. (2025). Generative Artificial Intelligence and Transversal Competencies in Higher Education: A Systematic Review. *Applied System Innovation*, 8(3), 83. <https://doi.org/10.3390/asi8030083>

Diercks, J. (2025, January 27). *Erkennt KI an Äußerlichkeiten das "Wesen" einer Person? Was man von "TheyseeyourPhotos" über das Thema Bias lernen kann...* <https://blog.recruitment.de/2025/01/27/erkennt-ki-an-aeusserlichkeiten-das-wesen-einer-person-was-man-von-theyseeyourphotos-ueber-das-thema-bias-lernen-kann/>

Ehlers, U.-D. (2024). Towards a future skills framework for higher education. In U.-D. Ehlers & L. Eigbrecht (Eds.), *Creating the university of the future: A global view on future skills and future higher education* (pp. 21–60).

Gonzalez, M. F., Liu, W., Shirase, L., Tomczak, D. L., Lobbe, C. E., Justenhoven, R., & Martin, N. R. (2022). Allying with AI? reactions toward human-based, AI/ML-based, and augmented hiring processes. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2022.107179>

González-Salamanca, J. C., Agudelo, O. L., & Salinas, J. (2020). Key Competences, Education for Sustainable Development and Strategies for the Development of 21st Century Skills. A Systematic Literature Review. *Sustainability*, 12(24), 10366. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su122410366>

Gupta, S., & Jaiswal, R. (2024). How can we improve AI competencies for tomorrow's leaders: Insights from multi-stakeholders' interaction. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 22(3), 101070. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2024.101070>

Haase, S. (2024). Future skills and (generative) AI – new era, new competencies? In T. Ahram & W. Karwowski (Eds.), *Human Factors in Artificial Intelligence and Computing* (pp. 177–187). <https://doi.org/10.54941/ahfe1005096>

Jääskelä, P., Nykänen, S., & Tynjälä, P. (2016). Models for the development of generic skills in Finnish higher education. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 42(1), 130–142. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0309877x.2016.1206858>

Karunaratne, W. V. A. D., & Calma, A. (2023). Assessing creative thinking skills in higher education: deficits and improvements. *Studies in Higher Education*, 49(1), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2023.2225532>

Kleimola, R., & Leppisaari, I. (2022). Learning analytics to develop future competences in higher education: a case study. *International Journal of*

Educational Technology in Higher Education, 19(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-022-00318-w>

Kong, S.-C., & Yang, Y. (2024). A Human-Centred Learning and Teaching Framework Using Generative Artificial Intelligence for Self-Regulated Learning Development through Domain Knowledge Learning in K–12 Settings. *IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies*, 17(17), 1–13.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/tlt.2024.3392830>

Lakera. (n.d.). *Gandalf | Lakera – Test your AI hacking skills*.
<https://gandalf.lakera.ai/baseline>

Liberating Structures. (n.d.). *Liberating Structures – Innovation durch echte Zusammenarbeit*. <https://liberatingstructures.de/>

Maznev, P., Stützer, C., & Gaaw, S. (2024). AI in higher education: Booster or stumbling block for developing digital competence? *Zeitschrift Für Hochschulentwicklung*, 19(1), 109–126. <https://doi.org/10.21240/zfhe/19-01/06>

Mejía-Manzano, L. A., Azofeifa, J. D., Rueda-Castro, V., Nicolás Otaduy-Rivera, & Caratozzolo, P. (2024). Analysing Future Skills adoption by top-100 Universities of QS-ranking: present and future skills opportunities. *IEEE Access*, 12(12), 1–1.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/access.2024.3520116>

Naseer, F., Tariq, R., Alshahrani, H. M., Alruwais, N., & Al-Wesabi, F. N. (2025). Project based learning framework integrating industry collaboration to enhance student future readiness in higher education. *Scientific Reports*, 15(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-10385-4>

Ng, D. T. K., Leung, J. K. L., Su, J., Ng, R. C. W., & Chu, S. K. W. (2023). Teachers' AI digital competencies and twenty-first century skills in the post-pandemic world. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 71(1), 137–161. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-023-10203-6>

Ornellas, A., Falkner, K., & Edman Stålbrandt, E. (2019). Enhancing graduates' employability skills through authentic learning approaches. *Higher Education, Skills and Work-Based Learning*, 9(1), 107–120. <https://doi.org/10.1108/HESWBL-04-2018-0049>

Peterson, C., & Seligman, M. E. (2004). *Character strengths and virtues: A handbook and classification*.
[http://www.idysinger.com/@books1/Peterson Character Strengths/character-strengths-and-virtues.pdf](http://www.idysinger.com/@books1/Peterson%20Character%20Strengths/character-strengths-and-virtues.pdf)

Podlaski, K., Beczkowski, M., Simbeck, K., Dziergwa, K., & Stawska, Z. (2025). Software development projects as a way for multidisciplinary soft and future skills education. *Cornel University*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2502.21114>

Rampelt, F., Matthes, W., Hannken-Illjes, K., Sandmeir, A., Gehrs, V., Horstmann, N., Kunz, A. M., Eigbrecht, L.,
Johannsen, T., Blum, S., Frank, S., Sutter, C., Koch, H. (2025). Future Skills 2030. Ein aktualisiertes Framework für Zukunftskompetenzen.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17910748>

Rottwilm, C. (2018, April 26). Vera führt 50.000 Interviews am Tag: Schlauer Roboter sucht Personal für Ikea, Pepsi und Co. <https://www.manager-magazin.de/unternehmen/artikel/robo-ter-vera-software-sucht-personal-fuer-ikea-pepsi-und-co-a-1204888.html>

Simon, J., Spiecker Döhm, I., & von Luxburg, U. (2024). Generative KI – jenseits von Euphorie und einfachen Lösungen. *Deutsche Akademie Der Naturforscher Leopoldina e. V.* https://doi.org/10.26164/leopoldina_03_01226

Soto, C. J., Napolitano, C. M., Sewell, M. N., Yoon, H. J., & Roberts, B. W. (2022). Going Beyond Traits: Social, Emotional, and Behavioral Skills Matter for Adolescents' Success. *Social Psychological and Personality Science*, 15(1), 194855062211274. <https://doi.org/10.1177/19485506221127483>

Tenberga, I. & Daniela, L. (2024). Artificial Intelligence Literacy Competencies for Teachers Through Self-Assessment Tools. *Sustainability*, 16(23), 10386–10386. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su162310386>

Tengai. (n.d.). *Recruitment AI Avatar Tengai*. Accessed January 17, 2026. <https://tengai.io/recruitment-ai-avatar>

Tengai. (2023, May 1). *Introducing the new Tengai avatar*. <https://www.mynewsdesk.com/tengai-interview-robot/videos/introducing-the-new-tengai-avatar-117935>

They See Your Photos. (n.d.). *They See Your Photos*. <https://theyseeyourphotos.com/>

Tondeur, J., Howard, S., Van Zanten, M., Gorissen, P., Van der Neut, I., Uerz, D., & Kral, M. (2023). The HeDiCom framework: Higher Education teachers' digital competencies for the future. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 71(1), 33–53. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-023-10193-5>

Toohy, K., Quince, Z., Walker, F., Furness, L., Bissett, M., Daley, C., Allen, K., Munro, N., Smidt, A., Wilkie, J. C., Horstmanshof, L., Baltrosky, K., & Naumann, F. (2025). Integrating Generative AI in Health Education: A Scoping Review and Implementation Framework. *Medical Science Educator*.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s40670-025-02578-3>

Wang, A., Yang, H., & Sengul, M. (2026). A Structural Model of EFL Learners' Behavioural Engagement in AI-Enhanced Classrooms: The Predictive Roles of Teacher Interpersonal Behaviours, Emotional Engagement, Perceived Classroom Support, and Technology Acceptance. *European Journal of Education*, 61(1).

<https://doi.org/10.1111/ejed.70441>

Wang, Y. (2026). Enhancing University EFL Learners' Writing Performance: The Role of AI - Enhanced Goal-Setting, Feedback and Social Norm Interventions.

Journal of Computer Assisted Learning, 42(1). <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcal.70179>

Appendix

Appendix A: Instructional Guide (Day One and Day Two)

Start	Stop	Duration	Topic	What	Method	Material
09:00	09:20	00:20	Opening	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduction of the lecturer - Learning goals - Discussing a <i>modus operandi</i> with the students using the 1-2-4-All method: “<i>How do we want to operate to make this lecture successful for all of us?</i>” - Documenting the resulting <i>modus operandi</i> on a whiteboard / flip chart 	1-2-4-All method (https://liberatingstructures.de/liberating-structures-menue/1-2-4-all/)	Whiteboard / Flip chart
09:20	09:45	00:25	Reflecting on Future Skills	<p>Self-reflection and peer interviews: “<i>What skills, beyond disciplinary knowledge, do you want to take with you from your studies?</i>” Students start individually and then exchange their results in pairs. The skills are summarized in a plenary session (e.g. on a whiteboard / flip chart). Several skills typically emerge that are part of the Future Skills Framework.</p>	Self-reflection and peer interviews	Whiteboard / Flip chart

09:45	10:00	00:15		Input presentation: Future Skills Framework	Presentation	Slides on the Future Skills Framework
10:00	10:30	00:30		Self-assessment of individual future skills using a survey. Students select three future skills they want to focus on.		Self-assessment survey
10:30	10:45	00:15	Break			
10:45	11:15	00:30	Foundation of AI I	Warm-up: <i>“What terms do you associate with AI?”</i> Students work in groups and write terms on post-its. In the plenary session, they place them on a wall and explain how they think these terms relate to AI.	Group work	Post-its / markers / post-it wall
11:15	12:00	00:45		Input presentation: <i>What is AI?</i> (history, definitions, overarching terms). Afterwards, a discussion on how the students’ terms relate to AI and what the terms actually mean.	Presentation and discussion	Slides: <i>What is AI?</i>
12:00	13:00	01:00	Lunch			
13:00	13:45	00:45	Foundation of AI II	Input presentation: <i>How does AI work?</i> (functionality, machine learning, deep learning, generative AI, optimization approaches). Joint discussion on how different optimization approaches affect results (e.g. positive human evaluation without necessarily being true).	Presentation and plenary discussion	Slides: <i>How does AI work?</i>

13:45	14:15	00:30		Watching the video “ <i>Gen-KI Basics</i> ” by Prof. Dr. Chris Biemann, followed by discussion: - What questions are still open? - What did you learn from the video? - What further risks can you identify?	Video and plenary discussion	Video (https://lecture2go.uni-hamburg.de/l2go/-/get/v/70983)
14:15	14:25	00:10	Break			
14:25	14:55	00:30	Foundation of AI III	Group discussion: Students explore where AI is already used in practice and collaboratively summarize their findings in an online table, including tasks, benefits, and risks.	Group discussion	Online table for collective AI summary
14:55	15:55	01:00	Prompting and technology-enhanced experimentation	Input presentation: Different prompting strategies (e.g. prompt chaining, role-based prompting, contextualization, tone variations). Students work in pairs and experiment with different AI tools to solve small challenges using each prompting technique.	Presentation and experimentation	Slides on prompting strategies; challenges (e.g. <i>Gandalf's Password: gandalf.lakera.ai</i>)
15:55	16:05	00:10	Break			
16:05	16:35	00:30	Ethical, societal, and regulatory perspectives I	Warm-up: Students receive three AI-generated personality descriptions based on three different images of the same person. In a joint discussion with the lecturer, potential risks of AI are explored.	Plenary discussion	AI-generated personality descriptions

16:35	16:50	00:15	Closing	Time for questions and outlook for the next day	
-------	-------	-------	---------	---	--

Start	Stop	Duration	Topic	What	Method	Material
09:00	09:10	00:10	Opening	Welcome and short energizing recap of Day 1, time for questions, and overview of the learning goals for the day		
09:10	09:40	00:30	Ethical, societal, and regulatory perspectives II	Input presentation: EU AI Act	Presentation	Slides on the EU AI Act
09:40	10:40	01:00		Group work: Applying the regulations, including obligations for providers and users, to a concrete case — implementation of an AI-based employee monitoring system for engagement and performance.	Group work	AI tool implementation case description
10:40	10:50	00:10	Break			
10:50	11:00	00:10	Deep dive into AI in recruiting	Warm-up: Discussion of students' feelings regarding the scenario: <i>"You apply for a job and receive an invitation to a short interview conducted by an AI avatar."</i>		
11:00	11:30	00:30		Input presentation: AI in recruiting	Interactive presentation	Slides on AI in recruiting

11:30	12:00	00:30		<p>Demonstration of a job interview with an AI avatar. Afterwards, pair discussion:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How did the interview feel from the applicant's perspective? - How user-friendly was the interaction? - What types of questions did the avatar ask? - On a scale from 1 to 10, how accurately did the AI capture personality and competencies? 	AI job interview and pair discussion	AI avatar: Tengai
12:00	12:20	00:20		Walking in the shoes of an HR professional: How should HR respond to these developments?		
12:20	12:30	00:10	Break			
12:30	13:00	00:30	Practice-oriented transfer and assessment	Preparation for the student assignment: Brainstorming a wide range of HR challenges that could be addressed by AI.	1-2-4-All	Post-its / markers
13:00	13:30	00:30	Closing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collecting takeaways - Explanation of the exam assignment (experimenting with AI in two HR challenges) - Outlook for Day 3 		